

FORMATION OF LANGUAGE AND COMMUNICATION COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE LESSONS THROUGH THE USE OF INNOVATIVE METHODS AND TECHNIQUES

Salokhiddinova Albina Narimanovna¹

Davlatova Madina Farhodovna²

¹⁻²teachers of the Department of Russian Language and Literature
Denau Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy
Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7441916>

Annotation. This article contains carefully selected material, interesting tasks of a creative and search nature, that help to foster students' interest in learning the Russian language, develop creative abilities, form the skills of educational work and the need to independently replenish their knowledge. A special place in the language system is occupied by the lexical level, since mastering the dictionary is one of the main factors in the development of speech skills.

Keywords: competence, innovative methods, techniques, material, tasks, learning goal.

The Russian language as a means of interethnic communication occupies one of the leading positions. Uzbekкционирующее в обществе узбекско-Russian bilingualism, which is developing in society, plays a positive role in the process of mastering the Russian language by Uzbek school students. Learning a language helps students adapt to changes on a global level, understand language values, and take a fresh look at the world around them. The main purpose of teaching the Russian language to Uzbeks and other non-Russian people is to help students master the knowledge of the Russian language and its riches, to equip students with the skills of free use of oral and written speech. Mastering a second language involves active speech activity, which is based on students' assimilation of a system of language units. A special place in the language system is occupied by the lexical level, since mastering the dictionary is one of the main factors in the development of speech skills.

We, teachers of philology, have a special mission—we lay the foundations for the spiritual and moral development of the individual. Today, the teacher should not only be a source of knowledge, but also an active participant in learning, be able to listen to him, make him his assistant, look through his eyes at the exciting problem—this is the teacher's task. The new age requires teachers to master innovative technologies and actively apply them in the classroom. Today's student skillfully uses a computer, understands technology. And our task is to direct their skills in the right direction, to show them how to gain knowledge, to interest them, to make them strive for knowledge with passion. The purpose of educational programs in the subjects "Russian language and Literature" is to form a functionally literate personality through the development of practical skills in the use of language units in four types of speech activity: speaking, listening, reading, writing; improving the language competence of students [1]. There are a number of tasks that contribute to the development of speaking and listening skills, which are also reflected in the methodological manual: - interviewing on pre-written questions and the ability to give correct answers; - understanding oral presentations and the ability to answer questions; - creating a dialogue on a given topic. Examples of tasks that contribute to the development of reading skills: - predicting the development of events at the beginning of the text or by heading; - introductory reading, reading to identify the essence and

details, reading to find information, reading for fun, reading to express a point of view. Examples of tasks that contribute to the development of writing skills: - presentation of the content of the text you have listened to or read, description of impressions about the movie you watched or the book you read; - writing a small message in the form of diagrams, labeled drawings; - preparation of interview questions. To activate the speech activity of students, color illustrations, story pictures, and various techniques are used. After reviewing the illustrations, the children choose a picture and talk about their favorite topic, based on their observations, using a pre-compiled thematic dictionary (for example: school, family, street, transport). I often use role-playing games such as "In the store", "In the theater", "At the doctor's", "Seasons", etc. to develop my speech and replenish my vocabulary. I always accompany any didactic game with illustrations, story pictures, visual objects, so that every child can feel, see, and pass through themselves. The conversation uses poems, riddles, and proverbs about nature, the seasons, and school life. Lessons in the form of conversation teach students the skills of conscious and active language proficiency [5]. Considerable attention is paid to the implementation of communication with the native language when teaching Russian, and I consider the translation of texts and choral pronunciation of words with specific Russian sounds to be effective. A high-quality audio or video recording can be of great help in pronouncing Russian sounds.

Thus, careful selection of materials, interesting tasks of a creative and search nature help to foster students' interest in learning the Russian language, develop creative abilities, form the skills of educational work and the need to independently replenish their knowledge. The current stage of development of the Russian language teaching methodology characterizes new approaches to defining learning goals and choosing specific technologies and techniques. This is in line with the competence-based approach, which is now recognized as one of the foundations of "Renewed Education". The concept of "competence" in the methodology of teaching Russian at school is primarily associated with the search for a more accurate, strict definition of learning goals, with identifying the levels of language proficiency, in other words, with answering the question of how the student uses the language. Competence – the ability to perform any activity based on the acquired knowledge, skills, and abilities. Competence in the modern methodology is understood as a set of knowledge, skills and abilities that are formed in the process of teaching the Russian language and ensure its mastery and, ultimately, serve the development of the student's personality. In the theory and practice of teaching Russian, the following types of competence apply: linguistic, linguistic, communicative, cultural *оведческая*.

Language competence is the ability of students to use words, their forms, syntactic constructions in accordance with the norms of the literary language, to use their synonymous means, and ultimately, to master the richness of the language as a condition for successful speech activity. Communicative competence is the ability to understand other people's speech behavior and generate their own programs that are adequate to the goals, areas, and situations of communication. The development of speech and language skills is carried out in all Russian language and literature classes: children answer questions, perform exercises, the teacher monitors speech, corrects where necessary. In order for such work to be productive, it is necessary to maintain the child's interest in making his speech competent, convincing, bright, expressive, and emotional. All this is achieved through increasing interest in the subject. To do this, I use a variety of forms and methods of teaching in my lessons: research

method, problem questions, riddles, fairy tales, riddles, crosswords, games, making sentences according to schemes, by a given beginning, and so on. The lessons use the following games-exercises: "Fourth extra", "Make up a word", " Replace the word is similar in meaning", "Correct mistakes" and others. There are always successful lessons where I use elements of critical thinking: for example, the "Right and Wrong Statements" technique. In order to arouse interest in studying the topic and create a positive motivation for self-study of the text on this topic, I conduct the reception " Do you believe...". It will teach children to think over what they have read and understand the "Thick and Thin Questions" method of writing. Questions of this kind arise throughout the entire Russian language lesson. I offer students a task: compose questions based on a textbook article, a work of art, and so on. "Thin" questions are questions that require a simple, monosyllabic answer; "thick" questions are questions that require a detailed, detailed answer. This allows me to shape students ' skills, formulate questions, and relate concepts. "Thick" questions "Thin" questions Explainwhy? Why do you think that is? Assume that it would be if... What is the difference? Why do you think so? Who...? What...? When...? Maybe...? Could he...? Was there...? Will there be...? Do you agree...? Is it true...? The children really like to formulate and write down questions for the work and ask them to each other. This work can be organized in pairs, groups, or individually. The "Insert" technique is also interesting in our work. It is used to encourage more attentive reading. Reading becomes an exciting journey. 1. Individual reading. While reading, the student makes notes in the text: V – already knew; + – new; - - thought differently;? - I don't understand, I have some questions. 2. While reading, for the second time, fills in the table, systematizing the material. Already knew (v) Learned something new (+) Thought otherwise (-) Any questions (?) They make short notes, keywords, and phrases. When filling out the table, students have a mini-summary. After completing the spreadsheets, students summarize the results of their work in conversation mode. If students have any questions, I will answer them, first finding out if any of the children can answer the question that has arisen. This technique contributes to the development of the ability to classify, systematize incoming information, and highlight new things. The "Keywords" technique is also very popular with children. These are words that can be used to create a story or definition of a certain concept. A word is written in the center, around which words or sentences related to the topic are recorded. For example: Snowstorm, counselor, Black spotBrainstorming allows not only to activate students and help solve the problem, but also forms non-standard thinking. This method does not put the child in the framework of correct and incorrect answers, students can express any opinion that will help to find a way out of a difficult situation. In order for the speech during the brainstorming session to be correct, children adhere to a number of rules: - 2-3 minutes are allowed for thinking and expressing their thoughts; - the statement cannot be immediately criticized and evaluated; - all answers are recorded on the board; - the information recorded on the board is analyzed; - the most optimal solutions are selected together. Reception "Basket of ideas, concepts, names..." I ask a direct question about what students know about a particular problem. For example, I ask children the following problem:-Write in 1 minute what you know about spelling paired consonants by deafness-sonority at the end of a word? At first, the student remembers and writes down in a notebook everything that he knows about a particular problem, this is strictly individual work (duration 1-2 minutes). Then they exchange information in pairs or groups. Children share some knowledge with each other (group work). Students are given no more than 3 minutes to discuss the topic. Students find

out where the existing ideas coincide, and what they disagree about. Further, each group in a circle calls some one information or fact, while not repeating what was said in advance. All information is briefly recorded in the "Basket" of ideas, even if it was erroneous. You can "dump" facts, opinions, names, problems, and concepts related to the lesson topic into the idea basket. Then, in the course of the lesson, these facts or opinions, problems or concepts that are scattered in the child's mind can be connected in logical chains. Receiving a mutual question and mutual learning. When working with weak children, this technique is considered very effective. It allows you to consolidate the material you have learned and identifies gaps in each student individually. It is easier for a student to answer his classmate than for me, the teacher: the tightness and fear of making a mistake are removed. I organize this work in pairs, and the correct and incorrect answers are always recorded. One of the favorite techniques is "Cinquain". In French, the word "cinquain" means a poem consisting of five lines, which is written according to certain rules. This technique develops students' ability to identify key concepts in the read text, main ideas, synthesize the acquired knowledge and show creativity. Rules for writing cinquain: 1 line – one keyword (usually a noun or pronoun), the title of the poem – the theme of the cinquain that defines the content. Line 2 – two words (adjectives or participles) describing the topic, expressing the main idea, words can be combined with prepositions and conjunctions. Line 3 – three words (verbs or adverbs) describing actions related to the topic. 4 line – four words – a sentence, a phrase showing the author's attitude to the topic, an aphorism in the form of a proverb, a winged expression, or a quote. 5 line – one word (usually a noun) – a synonym or association that repeats the essence of the topic, the word-summary. The Doctor is wonderful and kind. I listened, wrote it out, and helped. This man saves lives. The healer. The "Cluster" technique is used to structure and organize the material. Cluster – a method of graphic organization of educational material, the essence of which is that the main word (idea, topic) is written or drawn in the middle of the sheet, and the ideas (words) associated with it are recorded on the sides of it [3]. Children are invited to read the material being studied and write out key words, concepts, and expressions around the main word (lesson topic). And then, together in the course of a conversation or working in pairs or groups, children fill in these key concepts, expressions, and necessary information. For example: noun – grammatical meaning-morphological features – syntactic role; noun – subject - who? what? - gender male, female, middle, - proper, common- animate, inanimate-changes in cases and numbers-subject, predicate, complement and circumstance. Being a teacher of Russian language and literature in your classes I always set a goal: to see, to see, not to ignore all the best, thereby stimulating the internal motivation of students, so the use of innovative methods and techniques helps me a lot in this. They have a positive impact on the learning process and contribute to the comprehensive development of students. As a result of such training, students try to express their opinions, defend their point of view, enrich their vocabulary, expand their horizons, and change their view and attitude to the subject. During the lessons, they become more confident in their actions, conclusions, and achieve a deep understanding of the material being studied. My main goal as a teacher of Russian language and literature is to develop a highly moral, harmonious and spiritually mature personality, capable of creativity and self-determination. To achieve this goal, constant systematic work is required to develop students' speech in Russian language and literature classes, since it is these subjects that allow them to develop speech and language competencies more actively in each lesson.

References:

1. Standard curricula for the subjects" Russian language "and" Russian Language and Literature " of the Republic of Kazakhstan with updated content.
2. Bystrova E. A. The goals of teaching the Russian language, or what competence we form in the classroom. Russian literature. 2003.
3. S. I. Zair – Bek Development of critical thinking in the classroom: a Handbook for teachers of General education institutions. M.: Prosveshchenie, 2011.
4. Pedagogical workshops: theory and practice. Comp. by N. I. Belova, I. A. Mukhina St. Petersburg, 2004.
5. Mynbaeva A. K. Sadvakasova Z. M. Innovative methods of teaching or how interesting it is to teach. Training manual. A, 2009

